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Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Executive Summary

This report describes the industrial ecology system approach through Material Flow Analysis, the aim of which is to analyse the mass and energy flows within a system defined in space and time. MFA is a supporting tool for industrial symbiosis studies and is complementary to Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing. The goal and scope of the analysis have been defined, together with the boundaries of the systems under study. Process specification and activity mapping were performed for all three systems of study to better understand the processes and sub-processes, as well as relevant flows (inputs and outputs) and stocks between them. The data were collected with the implication of the partners developing the prototypes for the three industrial sectors (automotive, furniture and construction).

The MFA in this study was run for the current situation (also considered as the baseline scenario), in which the conventional material and products are being produced, used and disposed, and then compared with the circular economy systems and value chains that were studied in ECOBULK project. The aim of this analysis is to deliver a set of information about flows and stocks for studying and optimising closed-loop processes of the three prototypes studied. Through balancing inputs and outputs, the flows of wastes and environmental loadings become visible, and their sources can be identified.

The evaluations made took into account the available data regarding the circular scenarios with some assumptions to be made. Nevertheless, MFA reveals it's usefulness to visualize material and energy flows contributing to the environmental impacts of the system studied. This information however need to be linked to Life Cycle Assessment to have a complete view of the environmental impacts of the products.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	7
1.1. Description and purpose of the deliverable.....	7
2. Material Flow Analysis (MFA) methodology	7
2.1. Goal and scope definition.....	8
2.2. System boundaries definition	9
2.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes	10
2.4. Determination of Mass Flows, Stocks, and Concentrations	11
2.5. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks.....	12
2.6. Presentation of Results.....	12
3. Material Flow Analysis for ECOBULK project.....	13
3.1. Automotive sector	13
3.1.1. Goal and scope definition	14
3.1.2. System boundaries definition.....	15
3.1.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes.....	16
3.1.3.1. Linear model. ABS baseline #10.....	16
3.1.3.2. Linear model. PLA baseline #11	18
3.1.3.3. Linear model. PP baseline #14	20
3.1.3.4. Circular model. Alternative ABS/ECOBULK ABS-R2 #34.....	22
3.1.3.5. Circular model. Alternative P/E-T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38....	24
3.1.4. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks	27
3.1.5. Conclusions	28
3.2. Furniture sector.....	28
3.2.1. Goal and scope definition	29
3.2.2. System boundaries definition.....	30
3.2.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes.....	32
3.2.3.1. BAU scenario	32
3.2.3.2. CBM#1 Scenario: use of a biobased resin.....	34
3.2.3.3. CBM#2.1 Scenario: repair of one panel	36
3.2.3.4. CBM#2.2 Scenario: repair of two panels	38
3.2.3.5. CBM#2.3 Scenario: recovering the panels	41
3.2.4. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks	42
3.2.5. Conclusions	44
3.3. Construction sector.....	44

3.3.1. Goal and scope of the analysis.....	45
3.3.2. System boundaries definition.....	46
3.3.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes.....	48
3.3.4. Determination of Mass Flows, Stocks, and Concentrations.....	49
3.3.5. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks.....	51
3.3.6. Conclusion.....	52
4. Conclusions.....	53

FIGURES

Figure 1: Life cycle-wide flow structure model from cradle-to-grave and with circle-related loops (cradle-to-cradle) (source Bierer et al., 2015).....	10
Figure 2: Main process divided into subprocesses (source: Brunner and Rechberg 2005).....	11
Figure 3 The mass balance principle where k represents the number of flows in a system and m mass.....	12
Figure 4 Sankey diagram of the downstream part of the forest-wood MFA (source: Lenglet et al. 2017).....	13
Figure 5 MAIER's central console panel.....	14
Figure 7: System Boundaries.....	15
Figure 8: Flows and system boundaries for lineal model ABS baseline #10	17
Figure 9: Flows and system boundaries for lineal model PLA baseline #11	19
Figure 10: Flows and system boundaries for lineal model PP baseline #14	21
Figure 11: Flows and system boundaries for circular model ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34.....	23
Figure 12: Flows and system boundaries for circular model P/E-T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38.....	25
Figure 13: Prototype of modular furniture from Moretti Compact using cubic elements that can be used and reused for different functions (seating, storage, bedding).....	29
Figure 14: Business as usual scenario for the furniture demonstrator.....	31
Figure 15: Circular scenarios for the furniture demonstrator with repair maintenance (CBM#1).....	31
Figure 16: Circular scenarios for the furniture demonstrator with repair maintenance (CBM#2).....	32
Figure 17: Flows and system boundaries for BAU.....	32
Figure 18: Flow diagram for CBM1.....	34
Figure 19: Flow diagram for CBM#2.1.....	36
Figure 20: Flow diagram for CBM#2.2.....	38
Figure 21: Flow diagram for CBM#2.3.....	41
Figure 22: Example of multi-extrusion board with the core being coarse and cascaded material and surface primary scrap and recycled material.....	45

Figure 23: Prototype of a shelter using Conenor’s multi-extrusion boards and panels.....	45
Figure 24: The value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator in the reference scenario	46
Figure 25: The value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator in the circular scenario.....	47
Figure 26: Flow diagram for a shelter with the composite of Conenor in the reference scenario.....	48
Figure 27: Flow diagram for a shelter with the composite of Conenor in the circular scenario.....	50

TABLES

Table 1: Initial product systems proposals	14
Table 2: Relevant flows quantities for ABS baseline #10	17
Table 3: Relevant flows quantities for PLA baseline #11	19
Table 4: Relevant flows quantities for PP baseline #14.....	21
Table 5: Relevant flows and quantities for ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34	23
Table 6: Relevant flows and quantities for P/E- T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38.	25
Table 7: Flows classification under environmental point of view	27
Table 8: Product systems studied.....	30
Table 9: Relevant flows quantities for BAU.....	33
Table 10: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#1	34
Table 11: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#2.1	36
Table 12: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#2.2	38
Table 13: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#2.3	41
Table 14: Flows classification under environmental point of view.....	43
Table 15: Relevant flows quantities for the reference scenario of the shelter	48
Table 16 Relevant flows quantities for the circular scenario of the shelter...	50
Table 17: Flows classification under environmental point of view.....	52

1. Introduction

1.1. Description and purpose of the deliverable

This report describes the industrial ecology system approach through Material Flow Analysis, the aim of which is to systematically analyse the mass and energy flows within a system defined in space and time.¹ The MFA in this study will be run for the current situation (also considered as the baseline scenario), in which the conventional material and product are being produced, used and disposed, and then compared with the circular economy systems and value chains that are being developed in ECOBULK project. The aim of this analysis is to deliver a complete and consistent set of information about all flows and stocks for studying and optimising closed-loop processes of wood, textile and plastics from the car parts, furniture, and building components. Through balancing inputs and outputs, the flows of wastes and environmental loadings become visible, and their sources can be identified.

MFA is often combined with Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) (see, for example, Turner et al., 2016² and Medeiros et al., 2017³) to quantitatively evaluate complex systems from the environmental perspective. This report, however, is focusing solely on MFA while LCA will be conducted in T7.2. The data collection process though will be aligned with T7.2 as the inventory data collected for MFA will serve as an input for LCA in T7.2.

2. Material Flow Analysis (MFA) methodology

Although not as popular as LCA, MFA is also a tool closely associated with the discourse on sustainability and Circular Economy. MFA is particularly an environmental management tool that deals with the analysis of material and energy input and output processes, resource use and stock calculations, and hotspot assessment.⁴ At first glance, MFA has nothing in common with LCA. However, the MFA implies that less material loss will result in less material and energy input and thus a reduced overall carbon and other environmental footprint that can be captured by LCA. MFA hence serves as starting point for

¹ Brunner and Rechberg, 2005. Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis. Lewis Publisher

² Turner D.A, Williams I.D., Kemp S. 2016. Combined material flow analysis and life cycle assessment as a support tool for solid waste management decision making. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 129, pp 234 - 248

³ Medeiros D., L., Oliveira do Carmo Tavares A., Quixabeira Rosa e Silva Rapôso A. L., Kiperstok A. 2017. Life cycle assessment in the furniture industry: the case study of an office cabinet. *Int J Life Cycle Assess* 22, pp. 1823–1836

⁴ Balanay R., and Halog A., 2019. Tools for Circular Economy. In *Circular Economy in Textiles and Apparel Processing, Manufacturing, and Design*. Edited by: Subramanian Senthilkannan Muthu

more comprehensive environmental measures and environmental management accounting through LCA.⁵

Although not that standardised as LCA, there are some standard documents and textbooks, e.g. ISO 14051⁶, ISO14052⁷ and Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis⁸, providing guidance for running an analysis.

In this section, the fundamental concept of the MFA approach and the methodology are described. The application of this methodology to the ECOBULK project will be described in the following section. In some cases, the methodical statements must remain abstract, but they will be specified in the progress of the project.

The general MFA procedure is comprised of the following phases:

1. Goal and scope definition
2. System Boundaries Definition
3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes
4. Determination of Mass Flows, Stocks, and Concentrations
5. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks
6. Presentation of Results

MFA studies are iterative, which means that MFA operations are repeated throughout the project to provide the best results which can then be useful in helping with decision making.

2.1. Goal and scope definition

MFA begins with the definition of the problem and of adequate goals. This is where the main desired results of the study are identified and assumptions relating to the study are made. This step also ensures that the breadth, depth and detail of the study are compatible and adequate to address the stated goal. The goal and scope definition phase establish the context in which the assessment will be conducted.

An important element of the goal and scope definition is the selection of substance that are relevant for MFA. In the case of ECOBULK this selection is already defined by the goal and scope of the project itself.

⁵ Viere, T., Prox, M., M€oller, A., Schmidt, M., 2011. Implications of material flow cost accounting for life cycle engineering. In: Hesselbach, J., Herrmann, C. (Eds.), *Glocalized Solutions for Sustainability in Manufacturing: Proceedings of the 18th CIRP International Conference on Life Cycle Engineering*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp. 652e656.

⁶ ISO 14051:2011 Environmental management — Material flow cost accounting — General framework

⁷ ISO 14052:2018 Environmental management - Material flow cost accounting - Guidance for practical implementation in a supply chain

⁸ Brunner and Rechberg, 2005. *Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis*. Lewis Publisher

2.2. System boundaries definition

The system boundaries definition for MFA should be determined in both in space and time. Spatial system boundary is usually determined by the scope of the project (carbon balance of a community, MFA of a power plant, etc.). Often, the only possibility is to define system boundaries as administrative regions, such as nations, states, or cities, because information is systematically collected on these levels.

However, ECOBULK is a Circular Economy project which engages various partners from different European regions to create a closed-loop system for automotive, furniture and construction product systems. It hence cannot be limited the single organisation or region only but should instead take the system approach by looking at the whole value chain. Extending the scope of MFA/MFCA to multiple organisations is mentioned in ISO 14052⁹ and further discussed by Bierer et al., 2015¹⁰. The transfer of MFA methodology to life cycle-wide studies requires the following: (1) a life cycle concept has to be chosen and the actors involved in the corresponding value chain have to be considered (see Figure 1); (2) the relevant processes have to be identified and structured for building up life cycle-wide flow models that take into account the specific characteristics of the life cycle phases; (3) life cycle-related loops as well as intersections of phases have to be handled (e.g. processes like remanufacturing, re-use, and recycling); (4) data acquisition may imply the needs of gaining data from different actors in a supply chain as well as forecasting some mass and energy flows.

⁹ ISO 14052:2018 Environmental management - Material flow cost accounting - Guidance for practical implementation in a supply chain

¹⁰ Bierer A., Uwe Götze U., Meynerts L., Sygulla R. 2015. Integrating life cycle costing and life cycle assessment using extended material flow cost accounting. Journal of Cleaner Production 108, pp. 1289-1301

Figure 1: Life cycle-wide flow structure model from cradle-to-grave and with circle-related loops (cradle-to-cradle) (source Bierer et al., 2015¹¹)

2.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes

After selecting substances and defining system boundaries, process specification and activity mapping is performed for the system of study. The number of processes necessary to describe the system depends on the objectives of the study and on the complexity of the system. Generally, processes can be subdivided into subprocesses, and vice versa, any number of processes can be merged into a single process (see Figure 2). The outcome of this step is a complete map of the system under study with more detailed breakdown of different manufacturing and subprocesses processes, including all inputs and outputs, considered.

Also, a first rough balance of goods can be carried out for the system at this stage considering that data is available. Usually, material flows <1% of the total system throughput are neglected. Nevertheless, these small flows can make a significant contribution to one or more substance balances that are established later. Therefore, when in a subsequent step the substance flows are investigated in greater detail, it is important to check whether these small neglected flows are relevant in view of the objectives of the investigation.¹²

¹¹ Bierer A., Uwe G€otze U., Meynerts L., Sygulla R. 2015. Integrating life cycle costing and life cycle assessment using extended material flow cost accounting. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 108, pp. 1289-1301

¹² Brunner and Rechberg, 2005. *Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis*. Lewis Publisher

Figure 2: Main process divided into subprocesses (source: Brunner and Rechberg 2005¹³)

2.4. Determination of Mass Flows, Stocks, and Concentrations

MFA is heavily data-driven, and hence this step requires a detailed data collection (inputs and outputs) and analysis for processes, subprocesses and flows identified in the previous step. The search for and the collection, evaluation, and handling of data are core tasks in MFA. Primary data measured directly or indirectly on site is of greatest value for the one running an analysis, although mass flows could be also taken also from secondary sources (e.g. databases, regional, national, and international administrative bodies such as bureaus of statistics, industrial associations, professional societies, consumer organizations, national and international environmental protection agencies, journal papers, proceedings, books, company, national and industrial reports). Some material flows are assessed based on assumptions, cross comparisons between similar systems, or so-called proxy data. "Proxies" are figures that help in approximating or estimating the actual data of interest.

¹³ Brunner and Rechberg, 2005. Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis. Lewis Publisher

2.5. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks

The main principle of all MFA approaches is the mass balance, meaning that the sum of all inputs into a system has to be equal to all outputs plus changes in stocks (see equation in Figure 3). The mass-balance principle applies to systems as well as processes.

$$\sum_{k_i} \dot{m}_{input} = \sum_{k_o} \dot{m}_{output} + \dot{m}_{storage}$$

Figure 3 The mass balance principle where k represents the number of flows in a system and m mass.

A true material balance of a process or system is only achieved if all input and output flows are known, and if either = 0 or can be measured. If inputs and outputs do not balance, one or several flows are either missing or they have been determined erroneously. As for goods, the reason for a failure to balance can be missing flows; this source of error is eliminated when establishing the balance at the level of goods. Another reason could be errors in substance concentrations. Balance differences between input and output of 10% are common and are usually not significant for the conclusions.

Because data collected for MFA usually come from sources of varying quality and can thus be subject to uncertainty and in conflict with model constraints. These contradictions can be resolved by applying data reconciliation, a statistical method that helps to find the most likely values of measured quantities. While most of the model constraints are linear (e.g., mass flow balances of individual processes), in some cases also nonlinear equations (e.g., concentration or transfer coefficient equations) are involved leading to nonlinear data reconciliation problems.¹⁴

2.6. Presentation of Results

To maximize the impact of the MFA findings, figures that visualise the results and conclusions are of fundamental importance. Several standard graphs — flowcharts, partitioning diagrams, etc. — are proven means of illustrating the results. A flowchart is a drawing that comprises all processes, stocks, material flows, and imports and exports entering and leaving the system. This type of illustration, known as a Sankey diagram (see Figure 4 for example), is used to display material, energy, and cash flows. The figure should identify the system boundaries and the units of flows and stocks. This method of presentation allows the reader to check at a glance whether materials are

¹⁴ Cencic O. 2016. Nonlinear data reconciliation in material flow analysis with software STAN. Sustainable Environment Research 26, pp. 291-298

accumulated or depleted in the system and to identify which sources, pathways, and sinks are most important.¹⁵

Figure 4 Sankey diagram of the downstream part of the forest-wood MFA (source: Lenglet et al. 2017¹⁶)

There are several software tools available that facilitate the construction of MFA studies and Sankey diagrams (e.g Umberto, GaBi, Excel). Also, one such tool – developed by Paul Brunner’s team at Vienna University of Technology – is called STAN and is available for download for free on the web.¹⁷

3. Material Flow Analysis for ECOBULK project

3.1. Automotive sector

The automotive sector demonstrator subject to assessment in WP7 is the car central console panel (car fascia) developed by MAIER (see Figure 5). This demonstrator has been selected as it incorporates different materials developed within the framework of the project including bio-based ones, fibers (natural and wood), and recovered plastics and fibres. Moreover, it involves different project partners (BELLVER, AIMPLAS) creating a complete circular supply chain where the component’s material is recovered and re-introduced in a new component at the ELV. MAIER manufactures components for the major car makers in the automotive industry (e.g Opel, Toyota, Honda, PSA, etc.), and it is a well-established company in the market representing a common approach when it comes to business model innovation and transition towards circular economy.

¹⁵ Brunner and Rechberg, 2005. Practical Handbook of Material Flow Analysis. Lewis Publisher

¹⁶ Lenglet J., Courtonne J., Caurla S. 2017. Material flow analysis of the forest-wood supply chain: A consequential approach for log export policies in France. Journal of Cleaner Production 165, pp 1296-1305

¹⁷ <http://www.stan2web.net/support/mfa-basics/data-reconciliation>

Figure 5 MAIER's central console panel

3.1.1. Goal and scope definition

The Material Flow Analysis presented below is intended to identify the relevant flows and processes of the value chain of the automotive sector and, more concretely, the relevant flows and processes for the manufacturing of 1 unit of Fascia Central Console which is the reference flow considered.

In previous Work Packages (WP3 and WP4) the existence of different proposals made from the base materials ABS, PLA and PP reinforced with different materials or fibers is mentioned, as well as their respective alternatives where different proportions of recycled material are provided to the Back Side of the Fascia in question, were mentioned.

The results of the different tests carried out to determine the correct fulfillment of the functional characteristics, as well as the stipulated mechanical requirements, rule out each one of the alternatives corresponding to 100% recycled material on the back face of the components studied (#33, #35 and #37). The other PLA-based alternative System (#36) has been also discarded due to the inadequate behavior of PLA, which resides in the nature of the material itself and rules it out as a future material for the automotive sector.

For the different proposals made from virgin material, one has been chosen for each type of base (ABS, PLA and PP / #10 #11 and #14, respectively) in order to treat them as baselines of each branch.

Table 1 shows the different product systems considered. Systems #10 #11 and #14 (Baselines) correspond to linear models whereas systems #34 #38 (alternatives) correspond to circular models of the value chain on the automotive sector.

Table 1: Initial product systems proposals

Code	Material #1 (Front Side)	Material #2 (Back Side)	MFA
#10	ABS	ABS-GF8	Yes
#11	ABS	PLA-T10	Yes
#12	ABS	PLA-GF20	No
#13	P/E-T22	PP-GF30	No
#14	P/E-T22	PP-NF30	Yes
#33	ABS	ABS-R1 (100% recycled)	No
#34	ABS	ABS-R2 (50% recycled)	Yes
#35	ABS	PLA-R1 (100% recycled)	No
#36	ABS	PLA-R2 (50% recycled)	No
#37	P/E-T22	PP-R1 (100% recycled)	No
#38	P/E-T22	PP-R2 (50% recycled)	Yes

3.1.2. System boundaries definition

The Figure 6 shows the system boundaries considered for both models (i.e. linear and circular). Only the fascia central console manufacturing and end-of-life stages have been taken into account. The manufacture of the rest of the car components, their transport, assembly and any other phases related to the manufacture of the automobile itself have been left out of the scope of the study. In the same way, the stage of use and car dismantling it is out of the study scope.

Figure 6: System Boundaries

In linear and circular model, the material inputs flows of the manufacturing process (i.e. F1 and F2) refer to virgin polymeric substances (i.e. ABS, PLA or PP depending on the product system considered) and reinforcement materials (i.e. Glass fiber, mineral reinforcement or Natural fiber depending on the product system considered).

In the circular model, the fascia central consoles, once selectively disassembled from the car, are recycled. The EoL recycling process includes shredding processes, extrusion, and compounding adding virgin polymers. The obtained product becomes a useful material to be injected and it is identified on the graphic as flow F8 (ECOBULK R2 material). The flow F8 takes a value of zero in the linear model.

3.1.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes

The analysis at the material and processes levels for linear and circular models (including material extraction, material production, component production and EoL recycling) has been conducted based on the materials and information delivered by Tecnar, Maier, Bellver and AIMPLAS for all the product systems considered (i.e. baseline and alternatives).

3.1.3.1. Linear model. ABS baseline #10

The fascia central console ABS Baseline # 10 is made, among others, of 100 % virgin ABS (w/w) on front and backside, which means that, it does not have any proportion of recycled material. It is about linear model, baseline of the circular model ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34.

Figure 7 shows the flows and system boundaries for the linear model ABS baseline #10.

Figure 7: Flows and system boundaries for lineal model ABS baseline #10

Table 2 shows the relevant flows, their quantities and the information source for ABS Baseline #10.

Table 2: Relevant flows quantities for ABS baseline #10

ABS Baseline # 10				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Virgin ABS for front side	F1	0,1028	Kg/fascia	Maier
Virgin ABS for back side	F2	0,115276	kg/fascia	Maier
Glass Fiber for back side	F3	0,010024	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding ABS and GF, and extrusion	F4	0,0518742	kWh/fascia	TECNARO
ABS-GF pellets	F5	0,1253	kg/fascia	Maier
Natural Gas for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F6	0,39	m ³ /fascia	Maier

Electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F7	17,078	kWh/fascia	Maier
Paint P8227	F8	0,003	kg/fascia	Maier
Hardener P1040	F9	0,001	kg/fascia	Maier
Can (steel)	F10	0,0001	kg/fascia	Maier
Octavin (cardboard)	F10	0,004	kg/fascia	Maier
Pallet (wood)	F10	0,0003	kg/fascia	Maier
Fascia Central console ABS Baseline #10	F11	0,2321	kg/fascia	Maier

Based on the flows shown, 3 flows can be identified that could have certain impact from an environmental point of view:

- The Natural gas consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F6), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The electricity consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F7), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The virgin material consumption. (i.e. F1 and F2), due to its potential contribution in fossil resources scarcity among others.

3.1.3.2. Linear model. PLA baseline #11

The fascia central console PLA Baseline # 11 is made, among others, of 100% virgin ABS (w/w) on the front side and virgin PLA-M on the backside, which means that, it does not have any proportion of recycled material. It is about linear model, baseline of the circular model ABS/ECOBULK PLA R2 #36 which has been discarded due to the inadequate behaviour of PLA, which resides in the nature of the material itself and rules it out as a future material for the automotive sector.

Figure 8: shows the flows and system boundaries for the linear model PLA baseline #11.

Figure 8: Flows and system boundaries for lineal model PLA baseline #11

Table 3 shows the relevant flows, their quantities and the information source for PLA Baseline #11.

Table 3: Relevant flows quantities for PLA baseline #11

PLA Baseline # 11				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Virgin ABS for front side	F1	0,1028	Kg/fascia	Maier
Virgin PLA for back side	F2	0,14652	kg/fascia	Maier
Mineral reinforcement for back side (T)	F3	0,01628	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding PLA and T, and extrusion	F4	0,0673992	kWh/fascia	TECNARO
PLA-T pellets	F5	0,1628	kg/fascia	Maier
Natural Gas for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F6	0,39	m ³ /fascia	Maier
Electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F7	17,078	kWh/fascia	Maier

Paint P8227	F8	0,003	kg/fascia	Maier
Hardener P1040	F9	0,001	kg/fascia	Maier
Can (steel)	F10	0,0001	kg/fascia	Maier
Octavin (cardboard)	F10	0,005	kg/fascia	Maier
Pallet (wood)	F10	0,0003	kg/fascia	Maier
Fascia Central console PLA	F11	0,2696	kg/fascia	Maier
Baseline #11				

In the same way as in the previous case, based on the flows shown, 3 flows can be identified that could have certain impact from an environmental point of view:

- The Natural gas consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e.F6), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The electricity consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F7), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The virgin material consumption (i.e.F1 and F2), due to the natural origin of PLA and therefore, its potential contribution to the environmental impact categories related with land use and ecosystems toxicity.

3.1.3.3. Linear model. PP baseline #14

The fascia central console PP Baseline # 14 is made, among others, of 100% virgin P/E (w/w) on the front side and 100% virgin PP (w/w) on the backside which means that, it does not have any proportion of recycled material. It is about linear model, baseline of the circular model PP/E-T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38.

Figure 9 shows the flows and system boundaries for the linear model PP baseline #14.

Figure 9: Flows and system boundaries for lineal model PP baseline #14

Table 4 shows the relevant flows, their quantities and the information source for PP Baseline #14.

Table 4: Relevant flows quantities for PP baseline #14

PP Baseline # 14				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Virgin PP/E for front side	F1	0,080184	Kg/fascia	Maier
Mineral reinforcement for front side (T)	F2	0,022616	Kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding PP and T, and extrusion	F3	0,0425592	kWh/fascia	TECNARO
P/E-T pellets	F4	0,1028	Kg/fascia	Maier
Virgin PP for back side	F5	0,07707	kg/fascia	Maier
Natural fiber reinforcement for back side (NF)	F6	0,03303	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding PP and NF, and extrusion	F7	0,0455814	kWh/fascia	TECNARO
PP-NF	F8	0,1101	kg/fascia	Maier

Primer, Paint and thinner	F9	0,005	kg/fascia	Maier
Hardener P7421	F10	0,001	kg/fascia	Maier
Can (steel)	F11	0,0002	kg/fascia	Maier
Octavin (cardboard)	F11	0,0029	kg/fascia	Maier
Pallet (wood)	F11	0,004	kg/fascia	Maier
Natural Gas for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F12	0,39	m ³ /fascia	Maier
Electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F13	17,078	kWh/fascia	Maier
Fascia Central console PP Baseline #14	F14	0,2199	kg/fascia	Maier

In the same way as in the previous case, based on the flows shown, 3 flows can be identified that could have certain impact from an environmental point of view:

- The Natural gas consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing. (i.e.F12), due to its contribution in global warming potential among others.
- The electricity consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing. (i.e. F13), due to its contribution in global warming potential among others.
- The virgin material consumption. (i.e. F1 and F5) due to its potential contribution in fossil resources scarcity among others.
- The natural fibers consumption (F6) due to their natural origin, and therefore, their potential contribution to the environmental impact categories related with land use and ecosystems toxicity.

3.1.3.4. *Circular model. Alternative ABS/ECOBULK ABS-R2 #34*

The fascia central console ABS/ECOBULK ABS-R2 #34 is made, among others, of 100% virgin ABS (w/w) on the front side and a backside made of 50% (w/w) of recycled material.

Figure 10 shows the flows and system boundaries for the circular model ABS/ECOBULK ABS-R2 #34.

Figure 10: Flows and system boundaries for circular model ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34

Table 5 shows the relevant flows, their quantities and the information source for ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34.

Table 5: Relevant flows and quantities for ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34

ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Virgin ABS for front side	F1	0,1028	Kg/fascia	Maier
Paint P8227	F2	0,003	kg/fascia	Maier
Hardener P1040	F3	0,001	kg/fascia	Maier
Can (steel)	F4	0,0001	kg/fascia	Maier
Octavin (cardboard)	F4	0,004	kg/fascia	Maier
Pallet (wood)	F4	0,0003	kg/fascia	Maier
Natural Gas for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F5	0,39	m ³ /fascia	Maier
Electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F6	17,078	kWh/fascia	Maier
Fascia central console ABS/ECOBULK ABS R2 #34	F7	0,231	kg/fascia	Maier

Fascia to recycling	F11	0,0621	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for first shredding	F12	0,1540	kWh/fascia	Bellver
Electricity for second shredding and extrusion	F14	0,0472	kWh/fascia	AIMPLAS
ECOABS R1	F15	0,0621	kg/fascia	Maier
Virgin ABS for back side	F16	0.0621	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding ABS and ECOABS R1, and extrusion	F17	0,074	kWh/fascia	AIMPLAS
ECOBULK ABS R2	F18	0,1242	kg/fascia	Maier

Based on the flows shown, 5 flows can be identified that could have a certain impact from an environmental point of view:

- The Natural gas consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F5), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The electricity consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F6), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The virgin material consumption. (i.e. F1 and F16), due to its potential contribution in fossil resources scarcity among others.
- The electricity consumption for first shredding second one and extrusion (i.e. F12 and F14), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The electricity for compounding ABS and ECOABS R1 and extrusion due to its potential contribution in global warming among others (i.e. F17)

3.1.3.5. Circular model. Alternative P/E-T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38

The fascia central console P/E- T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38 is made, among others, of 100% virgin PP (w/w) on the front side and a backside made of 50% (w/w) of recycled material.

Figure 11 shows the flows and system boundaries for the circular model P/E-T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38.

Figure 11: Flows and system boundaries for circular model P/E-T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38

Table 6 shows the relevant flows, their quantities and the information source for P/E- T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38.

Table 6: Relevant flows and quantities for P/E- T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38

P/E- T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Virgin P/E for front side	F1	0,080184	Kg/fascia	Maier
Mineral reinforcement for front side (T)	F2	0,022616	Kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding P/E and T, and extrusion	F3	0,0425592	kWh/fascia	TECNARO

P/E-T pellets	F4	0,1028	Kg/fascia	Maier
Primer, Paint and thinner	F5	0,005	kg/fascia	Maier
Hardener P7421	F6	0,001	kg/fascia	Maier
Can (steel)	F7	0,0002	kg/fascia	Maier
Octavin (cardboard)	F7	0,0029	kg/fascia	Maier
Pallet (wood)	F7	0,0044	kg/fascia	Maier
Natural Gas for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F8	0,39	m ³ /fascia	Maier
Electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing	F9	17,078	kWh/fascia	Maier
Fascia central console P/E- T22/ECOBULK PP R2 #38	F10	0,234	kg/fascia	Maier
Fascia to recover	F14	0,0621	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for first shredding	F15	0,1540	kWh/fascia	Bellver
Electricity for second shredding and extrusion	F17	0,0372	kWh/fascia	AIMPLAS
ECOPP R1	F18	0,0621	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding P/E-T and ECOPP R1, and extrusion	F19	0,074	kWh/fascia	AIMPLAS
Virgin P/E-T for back side	F20	0,0621	kg/fascia	Maier
Electricity for compounding P/E and T, and extrusion	F21	0,0257	kWh/fascia	AIMPLAS
P/E virgin for back side	F22	0,048438	kg/fascia	AIMPLAS
Mineral reinforcement for backside side (T)	F23	0,013662	kg/fascia	AIMPLAS
ECOBULK PP R2	F24	0,1242	kg/fascia	Maier

Based on the flows shown, 6 flows can be identified that could have a certain impact from an environmental point of view:

- The Natural gas consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F8), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The electricity consumption for the 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing (i.e. F9), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The virgin material consumption. (i.e. F1 and F22), due to its potential contribution in fossil resources scarcity among others.
- The electricity consumption for first shredding second one and extrusion (i.e. F15 and F17), due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- Electricity for compounding P/E-T and ECOPP R1, and extrusion (i.e. F19) due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.
- The electricity for compounding P/E and T, and extrusion (i.e. F21) due to its potential contribution in global warming among others.

3.1.4. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks

The identification and determination of relevant flows for all the product system studied has been show in previous sections. In order to identify the environmental hotspots, a flows classification for the different product systems has been done. It has been arranged as follows, for each product system, the flows have been classified into 4 categories:

- Flows with high value and high or medium environmental impact potential (HV, HMI)
- Flows with low value and high or medium environmental impact potential (LV, HMI)
- Flows with high value and low environmental impact potential (HV, LI)
- Flows with low value and low environmental impact potential (LV, LI)

This classification allows us to have a qualitative idea of which are the hotspots flows from the environmental point of view. The impacts will be quantified in the life cycle assessment study.

Table 7: Flows classification under environmental point of view

Classification	Lineal Models			Circular Models	
	ABS Baseline # 10	PLA Baseline # 11	PP Baseline # 14	ABS/ ECOBULK R2 #34	P/E- T22 /ECOBULK PP R2 #38
HV, HMI	F6, F7	F6, F7	F12, F13	F5, F6	F8, F9
LV, HMI	F4	F4	F3, F7, F6	F12, F14, F17	F3, F19, F21, F15, F17
HV, LI	F1, F2,	F1, F2,	F1, F5		
LV, LI	F3, F8, F9, F10	F3, F8, F9, F10	F2, F8, F9, F10, F11	F1, F16, F2, F3, F4	F1, F22 F2, F23, F5, F6, F7

Blue: Gas natural or electricity input flows

Red: Virgin polymers input flows

Green: Natural fibers input flows

Orange: Mineral reinforcement input flows

Grey: Other for aesthetic finishing input flows

As we can observe in Table 7 the consumption of natural gas and electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing are expected to have high value and high or medium environmental impact potential in all the systems products assessed. The other electricity flows have lower values than the previous ones but high enough to suppose a high or medium environmental impact potential.

The virgin polymers consumption in lineal models has higher values than circular ones. The recycled polymers content in circular models is about 25% (W/W), so there are a slight difference on the flows values between both models. On the other hand, the virgin polymers used (i.e. ABS, PLA, PP) does not have a great environmental impact potential compared to the electricity consumption.

The mineral reinforcements and other aesthetic finishing input flows are expected to have a low potential environmental impact due to their low value and their chemical composition.

3.1.5. Conclusions

The MFA help us to carry out an analysis at the material and processes level for linear and circular models for the reference flow considered (i.e. one fascia central console).

Three linear models (being baseline product system) and two circular models (being ECOBULK alternatives product system) has been studied. For each product system studied, the most relevant processes and flows have been identified and determined, thus configure a first life cycle inventory that will be completed and assessed in the Life cycle assessment study.

Considering the flows' values and their potential environmental impact, a flows classification for the different product systems has been done, having a qualitative idea about the environmental hotspots of each product system. The impacts will be quantified in the life cycle assessment study.

3.2. Furniture sector

The Italian company Moretti Compact developed a new eco-designed modular furniture (Figure 12). The main idea was to work on the whole life cycle of the product: use of recyclable materials, preference for reusable components, utilization of elements suitable for disassembling and re-assembling simple lines and shapes and neutral colours. The main component of this modular furniture is a melaminated wood particleboard unit. Therefore this module can be used for different furniture items (seating, storage, bedding).

Figure 12: Prototype of modular furniture from Moretti Compact using cubic elements that can be used and reused for different functions (seating, storage, bedding)

3.2.1. Goal and scope definition

The Material Flow Analysis presented below is intended to identify the relevant flows and processes of the value chain of the furniture sector and, more concretely, the relevant flows and processes for the manufacturing of 1 cubic element which is the reference flow considered.

In other Work Packages (WP4 and WP8) different circular solutions were studied in addition to the ecodesign efforts of Moretti Compact.

The ECOBULK furniture sector demonstrator has two main circular economy objectives (see D8.3):

- Development of new low/no formaldehyde particleboard with a capability of incorporating more recycled content (wood).
- Production of modular furniture for testing new leasing business models that support product take-back, reuse, repair and material recovery.

From the MFA perspective, this study aims to assess and describe the industrial ecology system approach, including the mass and energy flows and stocks, for the Moretti Compact's set of furniture. The current situation (also considered as the reference scenario), in which the conventional product is being produced, used and disposed, is compared with the circular economy systems and value chains that are being developed in ECOBULK project, that includes reuse, repair and material recovery.

The aim of this analysis is to deliver a set of information about all flows and stocks for studying and optimising closed-loop processes of wood-based furniture made from particleboards.

Two different scenarios are taken into account (see Table 8):

- Circular business model n°1 (CBM#1): An eco-design scenario where the melaminated woodpanel is provided by KEAS which has jointly developed with AKZO NOBEL a low-formaldehyde solution;
- Circular business model n°2 (CBM#2): A leasing scenario where the product is not sold but rented, with a maintenance service.

The reference flow for the analysis will be one cubic element able to fulfil different functions (seating, bedding, storing) during a period of 10 years used on a daily basis.

Table 8: Product systems studied

Scenario	Short description	MFA
BAU	Business As Usual : Ecodesign furniture sold	Yes
CBM#1	Ecodesign furniture with a particleboard using a biobased resin	Yes
CBM#2.1	Ecodesign furniture with replacement of one panel	Yes
CBM#2.2	Ecodesign furniture with replacement of two panels and hardware	Yes
CBM#2.3	Ecodesign furniture with a recovering of melamine paper	Yes

3.2.2. System boundaries definition

In order to align MFA with the life cycle concept, study covers cradle-to-grave, including the premanufacturing (production of inputs), manufacturing, use and post-use (waste management) steps. Figure 13 provides the value chain configuration and system boundaries for the furniture demonstrator in a business as usual scenario with eco-design efforts.

Figure 13: Business as usual scenario for the furniture demonstrator

Two alternative scenarios were studied within the project:

- Circular business model n°1 (CBM#1): An eco-design scenario where the melaminated woodpanel is provided by KEAS which has jointly developed with AKZO NOBEL a low-formaldehyde solution;
- Circular business model n°2 (CBM#2): A leasing scenario where the product is not sold but rented, with a maintenance service.

Figure 14: Circular scenarios for the furniture demonstrator with repair maintenance (CBM#1)

Figure 15: Circular scenarios for the furniture demonstrator with repair maintenance (CBM#2)

3.2.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes

Process specification and activity mapping was performed for the system of study to better understand the processes and sub-processes, as well as relevant flows (inputs and outputs) and stocks between them (see Figure 16). The system takes the life cycle approach and is in line with the system boundaries defined in Section 3.2.2. It serves as the basis for the data collection in the next steps of the MFA process. The tool used for process modelling is the STAN2 freeware.

3.2.3.1. BAU scenario

The furniture is ecodesigned and made with traditional particleboard, which means it does not have any biobased resin. This is the scenario called Business As Usual (BAU).

Figure 7 shows the flows and system boundaries for the linear model ABS baseline #10.

Figure 16: Flows and system boundaries for BAU

Table 2 shows the relevant flows, their quantities and the information source for BAU.

Table 9: Relevant flows quantities for BAU

		BAU		
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Energy (Electricity+Natural gaz) for the manufacturing of a particleboard	F1	2,6	KWh/cube	FCBA
Additives (composition confidential)	F2	0,2	Kg/cube	FCBA
Wood particles	F4	7,3	Kg /cube	FCBA
Resin	F5	0,5	Kg/cube	FCBA
Melamine coating	F6	0,1	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste during the particleboard manufacturing	F8	0,3	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity consumption to cut the particleboards	F10	1	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the cutting of the particleboard	F11	1,78	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to glue the edge	F13	2	KWh/cube	Moretti
ABS edge	F14	0,165	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the application of the edge	F15	0,015	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for drilling	F17	2	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the drilling	F18	0	Kg/cube	Assumption
Hardware and glue for assembly	F20	0,36	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for assembly	F21	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Cardboard	F23	1,5	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for packaging	F24	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during packaging	F25	0,13	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to incinerate wood	F29	0	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity saved from wood recycling	F30	25	KWh/cube	FCBA

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of Moretti’s furniture regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- For a piece of furniture delivered, weighing 7,46 kg without packaging and 8.83 kg with packaging,
- The amount of waste generated in the company is 1,91 kg
- The amount of waste generated during the production of the particleboard by the supplier is 0,3 kg (the data related to the amount of waste for other components were not available)
- The electricity consumption within the company is 5,35 KWh
- But the total amount of energy necessary to produce a piece of furniture, including the supplier’s process for the particleboard is 7,95 KWh

To conclude, regarding material consumption, the level of material need to produce 1 cube is 125% the weight of the total weight.

This exercise focuses on the main material, which is the particleboard that represents 95% of the total weight of the cube.

3.2.3.2. CBM#1 Scenario: use of a biobased resin

In this scenario, one parameter only is changed. The particleboard is made with a biobased resin. Initially, data were expected from the experiments conducted by KEAS and AKZO NOBEL. Since the relevant data were not available, data were collected through Cranfield University who developed a biobased resin for particleboard manufacturing.

Figure 17: Flow diagram for CBM1

Table 10: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#1

CBM#1				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Energy (Electricity+Natural gaz) for the manufacturing of a particleboard	F1	2,6	KWh/cube	FCBA

Additives (composition confidential)	F2	0,2	Kg/cube	FCBA
Wood particles	F4	7,3	Kg /cube	FCBA
Resin	F5	4,9	Kg/cube	FCBA
Melamine coating	F6	0,1	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste during the particleboard manufacturing	F8	0,3	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity consumption to cut the particleboards	F10	1	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the cutting of the particleboard	F11	1,78	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to glue the edge	F13	2	KWh/cube	Moretti
ABS edge	F14	0,165	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the application of the edge	F15	0,015	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for drilling	F17	2	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the drilling	F18	0	Kg/cube	Assumption
Hardware and glue for assembly	F20	0,36	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for assembly	F21	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Cardboard	F23	1,5	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for packaging	F24	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during packaging	F25	0,13	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to incinerate wood	F29	0	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity saved from wood recycling	F30	25	KWh/cube	FCBA

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of Moretti's furniture regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- For a piece of furniture delivered, weighing 7,46 kg without packaging and 8.83 kg with packaging,
- The amount of waste generated in the company is 1,91 kg

- The amount of waste generated during the production of the particleboard by the supplier is 0,3 kg (the data related to the amount of waste for other components were not available)
- The electricity consumption within the company is 5,35 KWh
- But the total amount of energy necessary to produce a piece of furniture, including the supplier's process for the particleboard is 7,95 KWh
- Actually the main difference with the scenario BAU, is the quantity of biobased resin to produce: 4,9kg instead of 0,5kg

To conclude, regarding material consumption, the level of material need to produce 1 cube is 149% the weight of the total initial weight.

This exercise focuses on the main material, which is the particleboard that represents 95% of the total weight of the cube.

This simulation stands for a furniture used over a period of 20 years instead of 10.

3.2.3.3. CBM#2.1 Scenario: repair of one panel

In the scenario CBM#2.1, the leasing system includes a maintenance operation consisting in, during a lifespan of 20 years of use of the furniture, to replace one panel.

The company would offer a maintenance service consisting in coming on site with all the material needed to replace the defective element.

Figure 18: Flow diagram for CBM#2.1

Table 11: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#2.1

CBM#2.1				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by

Energy (Electricity+Natural gaz) for the manufacturing of a particleboard	F1	3,3	KWh/cube	FCBA
Additives (composition confidential)	F2	0,23	Kg/cube	FCBA
Wood particles	F4	9,4	Kg /cube	FCBA
Resin	F5	0,7	Kg/cube	FCBA
Melamine coating	F6	0,2	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste during the particleboard manufacturing	F8	0,4	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity consumption to cut the particleboards	F10	1,02	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the cutting of the particleboard	F11	2,28	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to glue the edge	F13	2,04	KWh/cube	Moretti
ABS edge	F14	0,20	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the application of the edge	F15	0,02	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for drilling	F17	2,04	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the drilling	F18	0	Kg/cube	Assumption
Hardware and glue for assembly	F20	0,36	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for assembly	F21	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Cardboard	F23	1,5	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for packaging	F24	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during packaging	F25	0,13	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to incinerate wood	F29	0	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity saved from wood recycling	F30	31,9	KWh/cube	FCBA
Particleboard used for repair	F32	2,48	Kg/cub	FCBA
Waste generated by the repair	F33	1,95	Kg/cub	FCBA

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of Moretti's furniture regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- For a piece of furniture which lifespan is extended from 10 years to 20 years by replacing once, one panel of the cube with, the extra flows compared to the scenario BAU are :
- For a piece of furniture delivered, weighing 7,46 kg without packaging and 8.83 kg with packaging,
- An extra 1.9kg of wood particleboard is needed, with 0,036kg ABS for the edges
- The amount of waste generated in the company 0,53 kg higher than in the BAU scenario (1,91 kg)
- The amount of waste generated during the production of the particleboard by the supplier is 0,1kg higher than in the BAU scenario (0,3 kg) (the data related to the amount of waste for other components were not available)
- The electricity consumption within the company is 5,46, or 2% more than the BAU scenario to double the lifespan of the service delivered

To conclude, regarding material consumption, the level of material need to produce 1 cube is 129% the weight of the initial total weight (in BAU).

This exercise focuses on the main material, which is the particleboard that represents 95% of the total weight of the cube.

This simulation stands for a furniture used over a period of 20 years instead of 10.

3.2.3.4. CBM#2.2 Scenario: repair of two panels

During a lifespan of 20 years, two panel of the cube needs to be replaced. In this scenario the metal hardware is also changed.

The company would offer a maintenance service consisting in coming on site with all the material needed to replace the defective elements.

Figure 19: Flow diagram for CBM#2.2

Table 12: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#2.2

CBM#2.2				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Energy (Electricity+Natural gaz) for the manufacturing of a particleboard	F1	3,8	KWh/cube	FCBA
Additives (composition confidential)	F2	0,3	Kg/cube	FCBA
Wood particles	F4	10,9	Kg /cube	FCBA
Resin	F5	0,8	Kg/cube	FCBA
Melamine coating	F6	0,2	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste during the particleboard manufacturing	F8	0,5	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity consumption to cut the particleboards	F10	1,04	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the cutting of the particleboard	F11	2,68	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to glue the edge	F13	2,08	KWh/cube	Moretti
ABS edge	F14	0,229	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the application of the edge	F15	0,022	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for drilling	F17	2,08	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the drilling	F18	0	Kg/cube	Assumption
Hardware and glue for assembly	F20	0,36	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for assembly	F21	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Cardboard	F23	1,5	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for packaging	F24	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during packaging	F25	0,13	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to incinerate wood	F29	0	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity saved from wood recycling	F30	37,3	KWh/cube	FCBA
Particleboard used for repair and hardware	F32	3,54	Kg/cube	FCBA
Waste generated by the repair	F33	3,42	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity consumption for repairing	F42	0,1	KWh/cube	FCA

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of Moretti's furniture regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- For a piece of furniture which lifespan is extended from 10 years to 20 years by replacing once, one panel of the cube with, the extra flows compared to the scenario BAU are :
- For a piece of furniture delivered, weighing 7,46 kg without packaging and 8.83 kg with packaging,
- An extra 3.4kg of wood particleboard is needed, with 0,064kg ABS for the edges
- To assemble both panels together, an extra 0,126 metal hardware and 0,015 vinyl glue is used
- The amount of waste generated in the company 0,9 kg higher than in the BAU scenario (1,91 kg)
- The amount of waste generated during the production of the particleboard by the supplier is 0,5 kg higher than in the BAU scenario (0,3 kg) (the data related to the amount of waste for other components were not available)
- The electricity consumption within the company is 5,54KWh, or 4% more than the BAU scenario to double the lifespan of the service delivered

To conclude, regarding material consumption, the level of material need to produce 1 cube is 156% the weight of the initial total weight (in BAU).

This exercise focuses on the main material, which is the particleboard that represents 95% of the total weight of the cube.

This simulation stands for a furniture used over a period of 20 years instead of 10.

3.2.3.5. CBM#2.3 Scenario: recovering the panels

During a lifespan of 20 years, the panels are still functional but the finishing needs refreshing. Thus the operation finished consists in covering all the panels with a new cover of melamine paper.

Figure 20: Flow diagram for CBM#2.3

Table 13: Relevant flows quantities for CBM#2.3

CBM#2.3				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Energy (Electricity+Natural gas) for the manufacturing of a particleboard	F1	2,6	KWh/cube	FCBA
Additives (composition confidential)	F2	0,7	Kg/cube	FCBA
Wood particles	F4	7,3	Kg /cube	FCBA
Resin	F5	0,5	Kg/cube	FCBA
Melamine coating	F6	0,2	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste during the particleboard manufacturing	F8	0,3	Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity consumption to cut the particleboards	F10	1	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the cutting of the particleboard	F11	1,78	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to glue the edge	F13	2	KWh/cube	Moretti
ABS edge	F14	0,165	Kg/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the application of the edge	F15	0,015	Kg/cube	Moretti

Electricity consumption for drilling	F17	2	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during the drilling	F18	0	Kg/cube	Assumption
Hardware and glue for assembly	F20	0,36	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for assembly	F21	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Cardboard	F23	1,5	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption for packaging	F24	0,35	KWh/cube	Moretti
Waste generated during packaging	F25	0,13	Kg/cube	Moretti
Electricity consumption to incinerate wood	F29		Kg/cube	FCBA
Electricity saved from wood recycling	F30	25	KWh/cube	FCBA
Melamine cover and glue needed for repair	F41	0,14	Kg/cube	FCBA
Glue needed to cover the furniture	F42	0,041	Kg/cube	FCBA

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of Moretti's furniture regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- For a piece of furniture which lifespan is extended from 10 years to 20 years by covering once the cube with a new layer of melamine cover, the extra flows compared to the scenario BAU are :
- The use of a melamine cover (0,1kg), and a resin (0,04kg)
- No extra waste is generated in the furniture company, other than the waste generated during the manufacturing of the melamine cover
- The difference in electricity consumption (due to the production of the melamine cover), 0,03 KWh

This exercise focuses on the main material, which is the particleboard that represents 95% of the total weight of the cube.

This simulation stands for a furniture used over a period of 20 years instead of 10.

3.2.4. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks

The identification and determination of relevant flows for all the product system studied has been show in the previous sections. In order to identify the environmental hotspots, a flows classification for the different product

systems has been done. It has been arranged as follows, for each product system, the flows have been classified into 4 categories:

- Flows with high value and high or medium environmental impact potential (HV, HMI)
- Flows with low value and high or medium environmental impact potential (LV, HMI)
- Flows with high value and low environmental impact potential (HV, LI)
- Flows with low value and low environmental impact potential (LV, LI)

This classification allows us to have a qualitative idea of which are the hotspots flows from the environmental point of view. The impacts will be quantified in the life cycle assessment study.

Table 14: Flows classification under environmental point of view

Classification	Lineal Model	Circular Models			
	BAU	CBM#1	CBM#2.1	CBM#2.2	CBM#2.3
HV, HMI	/	F5	/	/	/
LV, HMI	F2, F5, F6, F20	F2, F6, F20	F2, F5, F6, F20	F2, F5, F6, F20	F2, F5, F6, F20, F41, F42
HV, LI	F4, F8, F11, F23	F4, F8, F11, F23	F4, F8, F11, F23	F4, F8, F11, F23	F4, F8, F11, F23
LV, LI	F1, F10, F11, F13, F14, F15, F17, F18, F21, F24, F25, F29 F30	F1, F10, F11, F13, F14, F15, F17, F18, F21, F24, F25, F29 F30	F1, F10, F11, F13, F14, F15, F17, F18, F21, F24, F25, F29 F30, F32, F33	F1, F10, F11, F13, F14, F15, F17, F18, F21, F24, F25, F29 F30, F32, F33	F1, F10, F11, F13, F14, F15, F17, F18, F21, F24, F25, F29 F30

Blue: electricity or natural gas input flows

Purple: Wood or cardboard input flows

Red: Other materials input flows

Green: Waste output flows

As we can observe in Table 14 the consumption materials necessary to produce a particleboard as well as the other materials necessary to produce a full cube present low flows but medium to high potential environmental impacts in all the systems assessed.

The energy flows on the contrary have low values and low potential environmental impacts.

The use of recycled wood particles has a major influence on the global environmental impact of the product.

3.2.5. Conclusions

Given the limited access to accurate data, data from FCBA's experience and generic data from the Ecoinvent database were used.

The MFA help us to carry out an analysis at the material and processes level for linear and circular models for the reference flow considered (i.e. one cube). One linear model (being the business as usual system) and four circular models (being ECOBULK alternatives product system) have been studied. For each product system studied, the most relevant processes and flows have been identified and determined, thus configure a first life cycle inventory to be completed and assessed in the Life cycle assessment study.

Considering the flows and values and their potential environmental impact, a flows classification for the different product systems has been done, having a qualitative idea about the environmental hotspots of each product system. The impacts are quantified in the life cycle assessment study.

3.3. Construction sector

In the construction sector the collaborative effort of Conenor and Virol (wind turbine blade recycling company) resulted in the development of a new composite material made of wind turbine blade Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) waste. This is a first time ever when GFRP-waste is being recycled and used as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic composites. The developed material is used in the production of multi-extrusion boards, panels and decks (see Figure 12), which offer an alternative to wooden planks and pillars in outdoor use, with the core layer containing GFRP waste and the surface layer being primary scrap and recycled material (e.g. recycled HDPE- or PP-plastic from consumer packaging). This new weather resistant composite material will be tested in various outdoor furniture and structural construction applications, examples of which are presented in Figure 13.

Figure 21: Example of multi-extrusion board with the core being coarse and cascaded material and surface primary scrap and recycled material.

Figure 22: Prototype of a shelter using Conenor's multi-extrusion boards and panels

3.3.1. Goal and scope of the analysis

The ECOBULK construction sector demonstrator has three key circular economy objectives (see D8.3):

- To use waste thermoset composite as a raw material in outdoor furniture applications;

- To design outdoor furniture that can be dis- and re-assembled to prolong product life; and,
- To demonstrate that the product is technically recyclable.

From the MFA perspective, this study aims to assess and describe the industrial ecology system approach, including the mass and energy flows and stocks, for the Conenor’s waste composite components and how they could change and if one follows the waste hierarchy analysis. The current situation (also considered as the reference scenario), in which the conventional material and product are being produced, used and disposed, will be compared with the circular economy systems and value chains that are being developed in ECOBULK project. The aim of this analysis is to deliver a complete and consistent set of information about all flows and stocks for studying and optimising closed-loop processes of waste thermoplastic composite components.

3.3.2. System boundaries definition

In order to align MFA with the life cycle concept, study covers cradle-to-grave, including the premanufacturing (production of inputs), manufacturing, use and post-use (waste management) steps. Following the waste hierarchy principle, the life cycle-related loops (e.g. remanufacturing, re-use, and recycling) will be also incorporated into the assessment for the comparison reasons. Figure 23 and Figure 24 provide the value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator in the reference scenario and in the circular scenario.

Figure 23: The value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator in the reference scenario

Figure 24: The value chain configuration and system boundaries for the construction demonstrator in the circular scenario

The Conenor's product lifecycle is fed by the waste (e.g. materials outflow of thermoset GFRP products, such as wind turbine blades, boats & yachts etc), as well as other (primary or secondary) raw materials. Some materials could be sourced directly from the waste owner and grinded at the Conenor's facilities, while others (GFRP from wind turbine blades) may need pre-treatment elsewhere (e.g. sorting, shredding, etc.) before they could be supplied to Conenor. Conenor develops a feedstock (agglomerates) for composite components manufacturers (e.g. extruders, injection moulders and compression moulders) through addition of other raw materials. A possible intermediary step between component manufacture and end markets is product manufacture (design and assembly with other components for final structural applications), otherwise the components could go directly to distribution (e.g. B&Q, Kingfisher, Homebase, etc.) so that they could be assembled and installed on site either directly by the end-user (internal technicians) or contractor (external company). Following the waste hierarchy principles, the end-user may want to sell/give away/dispose (pay) the assembly either to:

- Another end-user for reuse in the same application.
- Another end-user willing to reuse/repurpose assembly/component in other applications (e.g. professionals, such as designers/architects/constructors that are looking for ways to reuse products and components in architectural/engineering projects).

The main end of life recovery strategy is mechanical recycling in the Conenor's or comparable extrusion processes, which is demonstrated as part of the EoL strategy for the construction sector. The extruded planks and panels are made substantially of waste materials and can be recycled into new planks and panels.

It is important to note that the value chain configuration provided in Figure 14 is hypothetical considering that (1) the products and solutions proposed by Conenor (recycling and utilization of GFRP waste as reinforcing material fraction in manufacturing circular thermoplastic composites for construction sector) are new with no market uptake as so far; (2) Conenor is a R&D company only acting as OEM for the sake of the project. This means that data acquisition for the MFA model will likely require secondary sources, as well as forecasting some mass and energy flows.

3.3.3. Identification of Relevant Flows, Stocks, and Processes

Process specification and activity mapping was performed for the system of study to better understand the processes and sub-processes, as well as relevant flows (inputs and outputs) and stocks between them (see Figure 15). The system takes the life cycle approach and is in line with the system boundaries defined in Section 3.3.2. It serves as the basis for the data collection in the next steps of the MFA process. The tool used for process modelling is the STAN2 software.

Figure 25: Flow diagram for a shelter with the composite of Conenor in the reference scenario

Table 15: Relevant flows quantities for the reference scenario of the shelter

Shelter - Reference scenario				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Materials needed to produce the composite	F1	1875	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Electricity used for the composite manufacturing (core layer)	F12	150	KWh/Shelter	Conenor
Electricity used for the composite manufacturing (surface layer)	F25	150	KWh/Shelter	Conenor

Electricity used for extrusion	F15	300	KWh/Shelter	Conenor
Waste generated during extrusion	F27	375	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Plastic used for packaging	F28	0,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Wood used for packaging	F29	30	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Metal used for packaging	F30	0,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Composite necessary for the installation		1500	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Steel necessary for the installation	F17	270	Kg/shelter	Warwick university
Ballast and cement necessary for the installation	F31	550	Kg/shelter	Warwick university
Waste generated during installation	F32	112,5	Kg/shelter	Warwick university
Energy consumption to disassemble the shelter	F20	0	KWh/shelter	Warwick university
Energy consumption of the EoL scenario	F22	0	KWh/shelter	FCBA
Waste recycled at the EoL	F23	270,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Waste in landfill at the EoL	F24	550	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Waste incinerated at the EoL	F25	1418,25	Kg/shelter	Conenor

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of the shelter regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- 2 701 kg are necessary to install a shelter weighing in total 2157,5 kg
- At the end of life:
 - o the baseline scenario generates 270 kg of waste which is recycled (with a theoretical rate of recycling of 100%), meaning a recycling rate of 12,5%.
 - o The total rate of valorization (recycling and energy) reaches 75%

50% of the electricity consumption is due to the manufacturing of the composite and the other 50% is linked to the extrusion of the composite planks. The energy consumption related to the manufacturing of the other components of the shelter (steel, ballast

and cement) could represent twice the consumption identified in

- Figure 25.

3.3.4. Determination of Mass Flows, Stocks, and Concentrations

No quantitative data have yet been collected for the product system in Figure 15, although a percentage distribution of material fraction constituting the Conenor's components is known. It is important to note that Conenor have tested over 60 samples with different material formulations and proportions. The most promising material fractions used, their quantities and formulations made thereof in Conenor recycled composite panels are presented in the Table 4.

Figure 26: Flow diagram for a shelter with the composite of Conenor in the circular scenario

Table 16 Relevant flows quantities for the circular scenario of the shelter

Shelter - Circular scenario				
Description	Flow	Quantity	Units	Informed by
Materials needed to produce the composite	F1	1875	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Electricity used for the composite manufacturing (core layer)	F12	150	KWh/Shelter	Conenor
Electricity used for the composite manufacturing (surface layer)	F25	150	KWh/Shelter	Conenor
Electricity used for extrusion	F15	300	KWh/Shelter	Conenor
Waste generated during extrusion	F27	375	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Plastic used for packaging	F28	0,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Wood used for packaging	F29	30	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Metal used for packaging	F30	0,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Steel necessary for the installation	F17	270	Kg/shelter	Warwick university
Ballast and cement necessary for the installation	F31	550	Kg/shelter	Warwick university
Waste generated during installation	F32	112,5	Kg/shelter	Warwick university
Energy consumption to disassemble the shelter	F20	0	KWh/shelter	Warwick university
Energy consumption of the EoL scenario	F22	0	KWh/shelter	FCBA
Waste (steel) recycled at the EoL	F23	270,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Waste (composite) recycled at the EoL	F33	1387,5	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Waste in landfill at the EoL	F34	550	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Waste incinerated at the EoL	F24	30,75	Kg/shelter	Conenor
Electricity consumption to recycle the composite	F36	0,9	KWh/shelter	Conenor

In complement to the conclusions given by the Life Cycle Assessment of the shelter regarding the functional unit and the system boundaries taken into account:

- 2 701 kg are necessary to install a shelter weighing in total 2157,5 kg
- At the end of life:

- the circular scenario generates at the end of life 1658,25 kg of waste which is recycled (with a theoretical rate of recycling of 100%), meaning a recycling rate of 77%.
- The total rate of valorization (recycling and energy) reaches 78%
- 50% of the electricity consumption is due to the manufacturing of the composite and the other 50% is linked to the extrusion of the composite planks. The energy consumption related to the manufacturing of the other components of the shelter (steel, ballast and cement) could represent twice the consumption identified in Figure 26. The recycling phase of the composite at the end of life does not modify significantly the flows related to energy.

3.3.5. Assessment of Total Material Flows and Stocks

The identification and determination of relevant flows for all the product system studied has been show in the previous sections. In order to identify the environmental hotspots, a flows classification for the different product systems has been done. It has been arranged as follows, for each product system, the flows have been classified into 4 categories:

- Flows with high value and high or medium environmental impact potential (HV, HMI)
- Flows with low value and high or medium environmental impact potential (LV, HMI)
- Flows with high value and low environmental impact potential (HV, LI)
- Flows with low value and low environmental impact potential (LV, LI)

This classification allows us to have a qualitative idea of which are the hotspots flows from the environmental point of view. The impacts will be quantified in the life cycle assessment study.

Table 17: Flows classification under environmental point of view

Classification	Reference scenario	Circular scenario
HV, HMI	F1, F12, F15, F17, F24, F25, F34	F1, F12, F15, F17, F25, F34
LV, HMI	F27	F27
HV, LI	F29, F31, F32	F29, F31, F23, F32, F33
LV, LI	F28, F30	F24, F28, F30, F36

Blue: electricity or natural gas input flows

Purple: Composite input flows

Red: Other materials input flows

Green: Waste output flows

As we can observe in Table 17 the main flows are distributed according to their level of environmental contribution and the level of the flow. The manufacturing of the composite whether it is about material flows or energy flows is the main contributor to the MFA.

The EoL scenario involving the recycling of the composite in the process at the step of extrusion would save energy and material. This first evaluation, taking into consideration a 100% rate of recycling, could contribute to reduce the level of electricity consumption by 50% and the consumption of material by 76%.

3.3.6. Conclusion

The MFA help us to carry out an analysis at the material and processes level for linear and circular models for the system studied (i.e. one shelter). One linear model (being the business as usual system) and one circular model (being the recycling of the composite planks at the end of life) have been studied. For each product system studied, the most relevant processes and flows have been identified and determined, thus configure a first life cycle inventory to be completed and assessed in the Life cycle assessment study.

Considering the flows and values and their potential environmental impact, a flows classification for the different product systems has been done, having a qualitative idea about the environmental hotspots of each product system. The impacts are quantified in the life cycle assessment study.

4. Conclusions

Material flow analysis (MFA) is a quantitative method for determining the flow of materials and energy. It aims to represent material flows schematically, based on the principle of conservation of matter developed by Lavoisier: the sum of incoming resources is equal to the sum of outgoing resources.

For the systems studied in the three sectors (automobile, furniture and construction), the most relevant processes and flows have been identified and determined, thus configure a first life cycle inventory to be completed and assessed in the Life cycle assessment study. Considering the flows and values and their potential environmental impact, a flow classification for the different product systems has been done. Simplifications were made given the limits of accessible data.

However, the feedback from this assessment is that MFA appears to be a powerful tool to sensitize companies about the global consumption of raw materials and the consumption of fossil energies throughout the life cycle and the value chain of a product. It can reveal the level of material input

necessary before the manufacturing of the product and afterwards. It also enables to identify the total amount of energy necessary to deliver a service over the whole life cycle of a product. In the three sectors the conclusions were different:

- For the automotive sector:
 - o The consumption of natural gas and electricity for 2k injection moulding and the aesthetic surface finishing are expected to have high value and high or medium environmental impact potential in all the systems products assessed. The other electricity flows have lower values than the previous ones but high enough to suppose a high or medium environmental impact potential.
 - o The virgin polymers consumption in lineal models has higher values than circular ones. The recycled polymers content in circular models is about 25% (W/W), so there are a slight difference on this flows values between both models. On the other hand, is expected that the virgin polymers used (i.e. ABS, PLA, PP) does not have a great environmental impact potential compared to the electricity consumption.
 - o The mineral reinforcements and other aesthetic finishing input flows are expected to have a low potential environmental impact due to their low value and their chemical composition.
- For the furniture sector, the material flows are important and business models enabling to repair some damaged component shows a great potential of savings in material consumption. The energy flow in comparison seem less important.
- For the construction sector, there are important flows of materials consumed during the manufacturing process of the materials, especially the composite and the total rate of recycling of the components can be very significantly improved with the circular model, enabling to reduce the amount of raw material needed, even if the benefit of the composite is also to use recycled materials at first.

The partners involved in the MFA did this very first assessment which creates a new area of thinking to mix LCA and MFA benefits in order to help designers to eco-design their products and companies to imagine new circular business models.

Moreover, for future projects MFA seems to be also an interesting tool to be used to visualize transport flows in relation with the material flows.